

DIGITAL ECONOMY: TRENDS AND PROSPECTS FOR BUSINESS CHANGE

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The concept of digital economy

The digital economy is a modern form of management in which large data sets and processes are digitally reflected as a key factor in product development and modern business. Applying the results in practice will increase the efficiency of traditional farm management. For example, it includes various automated manufacturing processes, 3D technology and cloud technologies, as well as the processes of growing, storing and selling goods using technology.

Here's what we mean by the transition to a digital economy:

- ❖ Building a new and modern society and economy revolution based on computers and technological knowledge.

ABSTRACT

The concept of the digital economy, its origins, advantages, prospects, dependence on business, commerce and cryptocurrencies, as well as the rapid growth of digitalization in education.

- ❖ Key features of the transition to the digital economy include social networks, modern sensors, and artificial intelligence technologies.

The digital economy is represented by:

- In the formation of artificial intelligence and intelligent control systems
- In the new monetary system and the expansion of banking
- In the development of e-commerce and e-business
- In the creation of new staff and new jobs
- and in the emergence of other very broad possibilities

Advantages of the digital economy:

- Access to global resources without intermediaries
- Trading through the global ecosystem
- Different digital technologies
- Intelligent online production

The fact that digital technology continues to enter our lives is one of the hallmarks of the virtual world. This is explained by advances in microelectronics, information technology and telecommunications. Thus, digitization is an objective, inevitable process that cannot be stopped. One of the most serious threats to digitalization is mass unemployment among low- and low-skilled workers.

Trends in Business Transformation through the Digital Economy

Digital business is the emergence of new business models that unite the digital worlds. The revolutionary changes are taking place.

Second, the number of digital banks and financial institutions that do not have their own offices and ATMs is growing rapidly. Key concepts of digital banking include customer orientation, the transition from the concept of consortium to the concept of digital banking, the development of CRM (Customer Relationship Management), increasing customer confidence, personalization of proposals and mobility. Digital banking services are observed in access to all spheres of life of modern people, first of all, mobile devices, social networks, information services, e-commerce, e-commerce and others. Digital banking offers its customers a wide range of digital

products and services using digital channels.

Miners and their importance in the digital economy

The miners, the creators of digital currencies in the crypto-economy, made huge profits from the growth of the bitcoin exchange rate in 2015-2018 and also suffered greatly from its sharp decline in 2015 and 2018. However, despite potential benefits from cryptocurrencies, many people and companies continue to draw their computer resources into the field of miners. Despite the fact that rising costs, especially electricity, are making it increasingly difficult to make a profit, there has been a dramatic increase in computer capacity in miners. Some members of the Bitcoin community consider miners to be a symbol of a prosperous life for themselves, and there are enough people who believe in it. Thus, the miners are currently at the stage of an "arms race" or "hashtag war". Miners are using high-performance supercomputers and algorithms to solve bitcoin math problems.

Cryptocurrencies - as an asset of the digital economy

The new digital economy has several types of financial assets, including cryptocurrencies. There are currently more than a thousand cryptocurrencies developed by different companies, and each of them performs a number of important functions in the field of cryptocurrency. One of these is the ICO (Initial Coin Offering), which can be used to raise funds for a project.

Business models of enterprises in the digital economy

The distributed open business model means that even if the company

leaves the market or the manufacturer is demolished, the Internet of things can continue to be self-sustaining. Blockchain technology allows anyone to create a roadmap for their own development and prosperity. The simplest conditions for participation in the digital economy are a mobile phone and access to the Internet. As mentioned above, blockchain technology allows you to create business models that allow everyone to become a participant in economic relations. There are three components to creating a blockchain company - its organization, financing and automate, simplify, and significantly improve market advancement. In the future, the cost of starting such a company will be significantly reduced, because the blockchain is a popular and reliable way to register a company. The property is visible to everyone and easy to keep records, which is especially useful in areas that are difficult to regulate by law.

Digital innovative technologies in the education business

It is recognized by many scientists and experts that the modern education system does not meet all the most serious requirements of our time. One of the main ways to radically change this situation is to widely introduce into the education system the latest software and hardware of modern technological development. One such tool is an open distance learning system on digital platforms that allows people to receive a full education without being separated from production and other daily activities. The modern educational process seeks to universalize using digital technologies, modeling people in education to be as similar as possible to each other.

How to learn through video games

For a long time, the issue of involving video games in the educational process was not given much attention. Many educators consider video games to be a waste of time, while others see it as a means of "spiritual depravity" or misleading the younger generation. Nowadays, it can be said that such passionate approaches are short-sighted. For example, we can cite the commercial video game PersuasiveGames, developed by Jan Bogost, one of the main theorists of modern computer games. Such computer games are commissioned by business, media and non-governmental organizations. Jan Bogost himself firmly believes that with the help of special games and life-appropriate game rules, it is possible to study the laws and problems of the real world and explain their possible solutions.

Now let's see how much the digital education system can change schools in the near future. In the future, once a person buys a tablet and places an artificial intelligence program on it, they will be able to learn without having to communicate with their teacher.

For example, the Duolingo service uses its own bot to teach foreign languages. The student asks a question to the chat bot and gets an answer quickly. But the rapid development of artificial intelligence could leave chat-bot and tutor training in the past. The Parla program, which is designed for learning foreign languages, is also a big step towards creating a digital teacher based on artificial intelligence. The educational technology in it analyzes the level of knowledge of the student, creates an individual educational program for him and adapts it to the student. According to

the developers of this system, the artificial intelligence program can find an individual approach to teaching for him, taking into account the correct and incorrect questions, the speed of solving examples and problems, the interest of the student.

According to a survey conducted by **Bot. Me: A Revolutionary Partnership PwC**, 58% of technology experts and business managers are - "teachers" they replied.

Prospects of digital economy

In the long run, a "digital" (electronic) economy could become a tool capable of realizing centuries old dreams of freedom for people doomed to hard physical labor.

Many people have a wide range of opportunities for creativity, science and art. The digital revolution is coming in earlier and stronger in some industries and countries, and later and less in others. Services, media and entertainment will be the first, followed by telecommunications companies and banks.

In addition, the "digital" (electronic) economy is an economy that exists in a hybrid world. The hybrid world is the result of a combination of real and virtual worlds, characterized by the ability to perform all the "vital" actions in the real world through the virtual world.

Here are some examples of key indicators of the digital economy in Uzbekistan:

- The advent of digital products and electronic services
- Creating digital platforms that will serve as the foundation of the digital economy
- Adapting the nature of consumers to the digital economy

- Emergence and development of new types of business models
- The emergence of new progressive models and mechanisms of production

Measures for the development of the digital economy

Nowadays, the digital economy and many of the effective technologies associated with it are rapidly entering our lives. That is why, the leadership of the republic has taken a number of important decisions to further accelerate the development of the state and society.

For instance, **the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 25, 2020, the most important priorities for the fate of the country in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, indicating the following tasks for the development of technology passed.**

According to the resolution, the following are the most important tasks for the further development of the digital economy:

- Ensuring close cooperation with government agencies and businesses in the implementation of innovative ideas, technologies and developments
- Creating a legal framework for the introduction of blockchain technologies, taking into account foreign experience
- Comprehensive development of cooperation with international and foreign organizations in the field of crypto assets and blockchain technology and the involvement of highly qualified foreign experts in the field of production

The conclusion is that the number of Internet users has now exceeded four billion. And the number of mobile phones has exceeded the number of people. Competition between companies and their nature is also changing dramatically. The capitalization of a company is directly

related to the number of its Internet users, the number of subscribers and the participation of interested teams. Therefore, the digitization of all sectors, including the economy, indicates that a new technological future is approaching us.

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